

Whitepaper: New Tools for Old Problems

Matthias Aßenmacher*

LMU München

matthias@stat.uni-muenchen.de

Mona Dietrich*

FAU Erlangen-Nürnberg

mona.dietrich@fau.de

Ahmed Elmaklizi*

LMU München

a.elmaklizi@campus.lmu.de

Eva Maria Hemauer*

Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin

hemaurev@hu-berlin.de

Nina Wagenknecht*

Georg-August-Universität Göttingen

nina.wagenknecht@stud.uni-goettingen.de

Abstract

The influence of "new" (or rather: digital) tools on research has been profound. During the workshop "New Tools for Old Problems" (09.01.2021), their place in the broader context of research and best practice approaches were discussed extensively, resulting in the following whitepaper. While the examples draw mainly from Egyptology, we would like to stress that many or even most issues also concern other disciplines, especially in the humanities.

Increasing connections within and outside research communities have shaped the cooperation of domain experts across different disciplines. The opportunities that digital tools made possible have changed the approach to research, including knowledge transfer and tool development. In our opinion, these challenges call for working in close interaction to exploit the full potential of such cooperation to benefit all involved parties.

Keywords: digital humanities · collaborative research · interdisciplinary projects · public communication · qualitative and quantitative methods · community exchange · egyptology ·

1 Cooperations

The increasing interconnectedness¹ between different disciplines, while undoubtedly a challenge for many researchers, offers a variety of opportunities. Nevertheless, scientific disciplines are regularly categorised as "qualitative" cultural sciences/humanities and "quantitative" natural or computer sciences.²

In this whitepaper, we do not want to deny the existing success story of the Digital Humanities. However, we argue that there is still much room for improvement when bringing together experts from different fields to foster interdisciplinarity. Digital Humanities itself is characterised as a field that can only exist in collaboration (Svensson, 2012) (although the nature of these collaborations is a disputed topic). In our opinion, the same principles could be beneficial in a broader field of the humanities.

When discussing interconnectedness and collaboration between different disciplines, we explicitly include non-academic actors, e.g. Big-Tech companies: Many notable milestones re-

*Authors in alphabetical order, all authors contributed equally.

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

License details: <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

¹I. e. emerging and expanding connections between disciplines not explored before.

²This divide is exemplified by the titles in (Blackstone and others, 2018) and (Bernard, 2017); approaches to bridging those poles include working on development of mixed methods (Creswell and Creswell, 2017), (Almalki, 2016). The division of *Natural Sciences* and *Humanities* is itself a relatively new construct, going back to the 19th century, as first proposed by Wilhelm Dilthey (Dilthey, 1959).

cently achieved in relevant fields were collaborative or industry-only research efforts. Below, we describe common pitfalls, difficulties and inhibitions as well as possible solutions and success stories:

Domain experts The term *domain expert* is often used approvingly – but also clearly states that the speaker’s expertise is acknowledged for only one specific domain (Costabile et al., 2003). While nobody can rightfully claim the title of universal expert, this preconception may sometimes limit research – namely, if everyone conducts research only in their domain of expertise without seeking collaboration.

Most often, the necessary expertise is split into two distinct groups (Costabile et al., 2003): On one hand, the part of the research community usually denoted as the experts for specific domains (e.g. Social Sciences or Egyptology); this group is, in most cases, equipped with superficial knowledge about data analysis from introductory modules on statistics or computer science from their Bachelor’s or Master’s programmes. On the other hand, experts from domains like Statistics or Computer Science do not necessarily come into contact with other scientific disciplines – like those mentioned above – before graduating.³ Success stories for both fields result from overcoming inhibition barriers and working together across domains: Obviously, these collaborations can offer fresh insights into the particular (humanities) subject. Furthermore, new types of data and applications also often trigger the development of new methods or models in the Statistics and Computer Science research communities.

To summarise, the aim is to bring together the groups of experts mentioned above; the central question to achieve this goal would be how to promote mutually beneficial connections. One such asset to foster collaboration could be pooling the different domain experts’ contact information and research interests. In practice, this effort has been successfully implemented by, e.g. the [Statistical Consulting Unit \(StaBLab\)](#) under Prof. Dr. Helmut Küchenhoff at LMU Munich. This unit focuses on connecting researchers from various domains (e.g. Psychology, Medicine, etc.) to its employees, (advanced) Bachelor’s or Master’s students of Statistics and Data Science, supported by members of the scientific staff of the Department of Statistics at LMU Munich. This consulting unit is nowhere near the only example: [The Göttingen Campus](#) is strengthening cross-domain cooperation between university and non-university research institutions.

Other – global and less specialized – approaches include the smartphone app *Paprr* (McKenzie, 2017), which uses a recommendation algorithm based on the rating scheme from Tinder. *Paprr* lets scientists rate abstracts of papers and matches them with other scientists. As stated in the article McKenzie (2017), the application is restricted to papers from [bioRxiv](#), limiting its ability to connect across different domains. Nevertheless, it is easy to imagine an application of such algorithms to a broader range of disciplines.

Common best practices and universal recommendations? Just as there can be no universal expert, there can not be universal recommendations. There is no one-size-fits-all answer to all research questions, just like there is no such universal method. Nevertheless, there are clear guidelines that researchers should stick to when working with data:

Thinking outside the box(es): The question of how to work with any data from the humanities is often divided into quantitative and qualitative approaches. However, this clear-cut distinction can lead to data not being used in the following analyses, as has already been argued for the example of spatial data (Baur et al., 2014). Thus, we would like to stress that the decision on which approach should be taken is not a ”either/or”-decision. Instead, researchers should use

³We acknowledge that other fields may be accessed by choosing to minor in them, both in humanities/social sciences and technical fields.

all methods appropriate for the specific data set and integrate the results if necessary.

Focus on reproducibility: Maybe the most important recommendation for working with software or data is to focus strongly on Open Science and reproducibility. It is crucial for sustainability and accessibility (cf. Sec. 2). Also, this issue is nowadays recognised and tackled by universities like the LMU by founding an [Open Science Center \(OSC\)](#), the [FAU Competence Unit for Research Data and Information \(CDI\)](#), or the [Göttingen eResearch Alliance](#).

Setting goals and overcoming inhibition thresholds The most crucial asset, aside from the professional expertise of all parties, is open and timely communication and realistic expectations. Especially the amount and quality of the available data must be disclosed to all involved parties upfront. Wrong or incomplete information regarding the data can easily lead to false expectations as well as poor choices regarding the analysis and the statistical modelling. Furthermore, a basic understanding of each other's domain is advantageous since it eases communication enormously if all parties communicate on common ground.

A great way to overcome inhibition thresholds, besides institutional or technical approaches, are workshops like the one this whitepaper is based on ([KOINet Workshop: New Tools for Old Problems](#)). Such informal and open meetings can significantly increase the interconnections between very different research domains. Events like these could be crucial in connecting researchers across various institutions. The experience at the workshop proved that digital conferences, in particular, enable researchers to partake in discussions, even across continents.

The impact of funding and industrial cooperations One fact often overlooked by young researchers and later a painful reminder to more experienced researchers is the necessity of good funding for proper and fruitful research. To get financial sponsorship for a research topic, it needs to be either:

- A well-known issue that the public faces; this helps bring in funding from public donations or - more commonly - from the government directly.
- A less known issue with few direct impact points on the general public; this reduces the possibility of getting funding directly from public grants or donations.

The former point is rather obvious, so we will not elaborate upon it much. After all, there is no need to explain the benefit of these research findings, e.g., better ways of treating cancer. It is a self-explanatory issue, and almost everyone would have a direct and emotional link to it. The latter case is more complicated. Explaining the importance of mapping our location in the cosmos to the general public could prove a challenge. Not because the theories are complex and demanding - instead, the problem lies in finding the emotional link to the issue at hand and mapping out the direct benefit to the public from researching that issue. The humanities generally face this problem even more than applied and natural sciences ([Haydar, 2021](#)).

In recent years, an alternative to the necessity of selling an idea to the general public has opened up since a lot of the funding comes from companies/industries. In that regard, applied and natural sciences could integrate themselves quite nicely due to their inherent nature of being close to the implementation part ([Jagadeesh et al., 2022](#); [Dean, 2022](#)), meaning that they are closer to real-life products and can be marketed to the public with greater ease. Hence, getting back a return on investment from the companies is more realistic. The dilemma then becomes finding a common theme for both a company and a research institute. A prime example of a success story in that regard is the game *Assassin's Creed: Origin* ([Poiron, 2021](#)). Maybe video games are not the most traditional way of spending research resources. However, this needs to be seen from all perspectives to judge the issue correctly:

- *From companies/industry point of view:* The company responsible for the game has won the recognition of having made a game based on historical events. This factor helped the marketing of the product to increase the degree of public awareness.
- *From the public point of view:* The amount of interest that the game has generated in the history of Egypt and its monuments was immense (Maguid, 2021). Even among those who initially had some interest in Egyptology, the game took this interest to a new level. The stunning imagery had a significant part in the public's reception. For the first time, it facilitated imagining and visualising the sceneries of daily life in ancient Egypt realistically. The possibility to view history as if we had a virtual time machine adds immensely to the arsenal of historians (Casey, 2021). Even the fantasy parts located in the ancient Egyptian afterworld included how the ancient Egyptians imagined the afterlife in intrinsic detail. Similarly, projects under the general heading of the European Time Machine project endeavour to reconstruct and re-contextualise the past (Organisation, 2022).
- *From the researcher's point of view:* Aside from any financial aspects of the project, where the research institutes could acquire more funding, the amount of public interest gathered and directed into the disciplines of archaeology and Egyptology was a great boon (Gonchar, 2020). The tools/games were even used as an educational means afterwards.

With the completed picture, it becomes evident that this was a win-win situation for all parties involved, from the private sector to society as a whole, as well as the research institutes. Nevertheless, our example is still a cherry-picked success story, and we do not claim that the experience from this project can be generalised across other disciplines and projects. However, it still showcases a wide range of how stakeholders can integrate research with industrial interests.

Further examples for successful cooperation As we show below, new tools offer many scientifically interesting possibilities for – in our case – Egyptology and Ancient Studies to prepare, process, and present data. In terms of interconnection between two research fields, the natural or computational sciences should also benefit from cooperation: The applicability of numerous sociological, political, cultural, and anthropological theories in archaeology can help to readjust, sharpen and refine their theories and methodologies – but the natural sciences can also benefit from the diversity of the data and their methods tap into their general applicability. The collaboration between computer science, which needs data to test and develop new state-of-the-art techniques, and archaeology has proven to be particularly productive; for example, in the virtual reconstruction of Pi-Ramesses, the capital of the famous ruler Ramesses II and largely demolished in antiquity. The impressive virtual reconstruction of the city is based on large-scale photogrammetric measurements and targeted archaeological investigations (Badisches Landesmuseum Karlsruhe, Roemer-Pelizaeus Museum Hildesheim, Qantir Excavation Project, 2019). Another example of fruitful cooperation between humanities and computer sciences representatives is the e-Learning project "Thot 2.0" by Prof. Dr Francois Bry and Prof. Dr Julia Budka from LMU Munich (Budka et al., 2016). There are, in our opinion, still more fields from the loosely defined group of "disciplines in the humanities" where such cooperation might prove effective. This cooperation is particularly evident in the Digital Humanities, where interdisciplinarity is embedded in the subject's definition (Sahle, 2015).

Dealing with (over)hyped topics and criticism Despite advanced statistical methods being helpful in many cases, we also want to add a word of caution. In recent years, there has been a lot of hype around some buzz topics like Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning, Blockchain or Virtual Reality (to name a few). But instead of running after these (potentially over-)hyped

topics, good interdisciplinary research, in our opinion, stands out as an appropriate application of (advanced) methodologies to practical, real-world problems. We want to shed light on developments like these by using recent advancements in the field of Natural Language Processing (NLP) as examples:

Since the advent of word vector representations (Mikolov et al., 2013) (a.k.a. word embeddings) in the earlier half of the last century, the field has been developing at lightning speed. The use of graphics processing units (GPUs), at first in Computer Vision for training deep neural networks, was adopted and has been partly superseded by the even more powerful tensor processing units (TPUs). These developments made it possible to train always larger (and better) architectures, preliminarily culminating in the introduction of BERT (Devlin et al., 2019) (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers). At the time of writing, BERT has already been adapted and improved many times but still can be seen as the one architecture that changes the way researchers approach NLP problems. Today's largest models exceed BERT's size by orders of magnitude, requiring enormous computational resources, unfortunately not readily available to everyone despite the exponential growth of computational power (Moore and others, 1965). On the other hand, several free resources are available to scholars (or even anybody), which might not be used due to a lack of knowledge. Tech companies like Google⁴ or Amazon⁵ offer cloud computing services (partly) for free, providing even access to GPUs. The LRZ can be mentioned as one of the larger institutions providing computational resources to universities in the public sector.⁶

These – undoubtedly great – achievements lead to a largely justified hype around this topic and many researchers wanting to apply the latest methods. And that is precisely where domain experts get into the game: Their in-depth knowledge about the different architectures as well as their strengths, weaknesses or associated requirements facilitates more informed decisions regarding model choice. This understanding also ties in with questions of implementation, which we will discuss below. For solving research questions, always using the latest high-end architecture with up to billions of model parameters, e.g. GPT-3 (Brown et al., 2020), might, however, in many cases, be like using a sledgehammer to crack a nut. Carefully weighing the complexity of the research questions against the computational expense and the complexity of the model is something that can be very well - collaboratively - achieved by the cooperation of domain experts.

The "trend after the trend" As just one example: IT networking is undoubtedly becoming increasingly important (e.g. in autonomous driving (Wang et al., 2019)). The compatibility of data management systems and communication channels is crucial for these applications. Even though standards have been provided, this topic has not been adopted in the humanities. However, networking will increasingly prove to be a problem in the coming years when trying to merge the results of various database projects.⁷ During the transfer and consolidation of literature databases, for example, it has been shown that due to incompatibility of saved formats and the errors that arise during data imports, subsequent manual improvements and refinements are still necessary (such as in the case of openRefine⁸). In the future – on the one hand – the establishment of shared platforms and data standards for different databases or file management systems and applications should be given special attention; on the other hand, existing and new projects should have common standards set to enable the merging of results. Another trend is

⁴<https://colab.research.google.com/>

⁵<https://aws.amazon.com/de/education/awseducate/code-org/>

⁶<https://doku.lrz.de/display/PUBLIC/High+Performance+Computing>

⁷A project that aims to standardize excavation databases by providing a database format is <https://www.researchspace.org/>.

⁸<https://openrefine.org/>

machine learning and artificial intelligence (cf. *Dealing with (over-)hyped topics and criticism* in Sec. 1). However, the problem with these applications is that most of them are very "data-hungry" and have, up to this point, been unusable for many corpora due to insufficient quantity. This problem will be addressed in more detail in Sec. 2 below.

2 Implementation

Planning for digital tools and sustainability When implementing these new methods and tools, we would like to propose that sustainability also be part of the planning process. Especially in the case of software, these considerations should explicitly include code maintenance and documentation (Anonymous, 2006; Anonymous, 2022). While a single-use programme might work for a specific task, even in the case of so-called cowboy programming, any further research development using this tool might fail due to ineffective code or outdated third-party components, which would need to be regularly updated. We would also like to question if such limited tools effectively utilise researchers' often limited resources. The parameters we discuss here have also recently been taken up by developments in the field of research data management and have, as a result, been taken up by several research data management policies and repositories (e.g. Ianus FDZ⁹). Nevertheless, software and data produced by that software are two different aspects of implementing tools. Thus, differentiating between them might be useful in terms of parameters for planning a new project.

However, with the increasing integration of information technology tools for processing and displaying data, the problem of sustainability has emerged as a key question when working with software. Websites must be hosted, managed, and regularly maintained – this has resulted in some projects with extensive online databases going offline after the project funding ended. These losses are especially problematic for young researchers. For example, several database projects, such as Prosopographia Memphitica (Herzberg, 2019), could no longer be published or hosted after the dissolution of the Graduate School TOPOI (Berliner Antike Kolleg, 2013). The latter is currently hosted via GitHub. The scientific benefit for the research community is lost when the data is no longer available. A significant challenge for these projects is to guarantee the security and availability of their data for a longer period of time than project funding allows (Neuroth et al., 2012, 316).

The case for open-source software The accessibility of the code or software also considerably improves the transparency and credibility of any research results as it makes them verifiable (Gundersen, 2020). Recently, projects have often used GitHub as a way to document their code and as a convenient way to build a project with a team. In the case of open-source software, many licenses do allow for development, modification, and extension (potentially under the same conditions as the previous license) (Massachusetts Institute of Technology, 1988; Smith, 2007). An example of using these kinds of open licenses would be the recent publication of the AED-TEI (Schweitzer, 2018), which includes a TEI format for Ancient Egyptian texts. Making both the data and the format available to the entire research community enables everyone to connect their findings within the broader context of the discipline. While an open-source model might not work for every project, we believe it should be considered whenever a new research tool or data format is developed. Especially with software, it might even be the most effective use of existing resources and facilitate the broader research community's involvement.

Cooperative development of tools and methods So far, Ancient Studies have often contented themselves with applying already developed tools to their material long after their conceptions. The first systems for mass data processing were used as early as the 1960s, and the

⁹<https://www.ianus-fdz.de/>

requirements for database systems that are still valid today were already introduced by Edgar Frank Codd in 1970 (Codd, 1983). In classical studies, however, databases did not become popular until the 2000s (Adams and Strudwick, 2009). The same is now the case with the current virtual reality and 3D models trend: VR has been an integral part of innovation and technology fairs for 20 years. Video game developers have even been using three-dimensional display methods increasingly since the 1980s (Shane McComas, 2018). Although the humanities are involved in various cooperation projects in the (further) development of sub-applications and specific programs, they do not influence general trends. For the most part, they are mere users of existing tools and don't actively participate in developing new tools that depend on the needs and requirements of the humanities. These issues have also been addressed, in part, in the context of the *Digital Turn* (Wolff, 2015). Thus, the following question arises: How can humanities scholars participate in the development of new technological tools? And how can cooperation between the humanities and natural sciences be institutionalised in this area?

A prerequisite is the regular and organised exchange of interested parties via newsletters, joint conferences, workshops, inter- and intra-university ideas panels to build up the connections necessary for this kind of participation. Additionally, in our opinion, there is a need for a networking platform on a student level to break down inhibitions and soften specialist boundaries. Newly established fields, especially Digital Humanities, are in the perfect position to facilitate exchange across disciplines. More extensive, innovative joint projects can be set up based on the networks these new subjects provide. For this purpose, and also to counteract the problem of orphaned database projects, it is, however, also necessary to set up competence centres, such as the [ArchäoBioCenter](#) or the [IT-Gruppe Geisteswissenschaften](#) in Munich: structures that enable close networking and interaction, offer a platform for exchange but are additionally firmly institutionalised so that they can reliably take on tasks such as data management and security.

Data scarcity in Egyptology However, many of the proposed digital tools and methods are designed for much larger data sets than Egyptology. For example, the 2014 version of the *Thesaurus Linguae Aegyptiae* consisted of 1.200.000 corpus words (Seidlmayer, 2021), a number dwarfed by conventional Language Datasets in use for modern languages (see sec. 1). This means that working with data in Egyptology (and, of course, any similar subject) poses the problem of being far too sparse for conventional software usage. There are two possible solutions:

Creating new data The Hieroglyphics Initiative project, a research project by Ubisoft in cooperation with Google, has set itself to develop a [hieroglyphic decipherer](#). However, since the existing hieroglyphic material is insufficient to train an AI, the project called on volunteers to (re-)draw hieroglyphics themselves and thus expanded the data material. Valérie Angenot's "Eye-tracking Egypt" project¹⁰ follows a similar approach. Experts from various disciplines work together to decipher the "reading" of Egyptian images by recording the eye movements of test subjects with different knowledge of Egyptian images. The other possibility is to expand the usage of data already available:

Utilizing the available data and making recording loss-free For this, it is necessary to establish new investigation and excavation methods, such as ceramic scans, findings, drones, and micro-examinations, train the archaeologists accordingly and help develop the latest methods for capturing the smallest traces. Handheld devices expand their functionality as well: The coffee machine can already be switched on with smartphones and smart home systems. Globally, the users of smartphones currently by far exceed those of conventional personal computers. In

¹⁰<https://professeurs.uqam.ca/professeur/angenot.valerie/>

the case of forms of presentation and new formats, it should always be considered whether the respective application can also be made available or usable via smartphone.¹¹

Key questions for implementing new tools As stated above, we argue that the capabilities of methods and, by extension, tools should be carefully considered and tailored to each research project's needs. These considerations include critical reflection on the tool's usefulness: Is there an actual benefit? How would this benefit be measured? And lastly, how does it compare to the cost of developing the tool? If conventional, established methods could also answer the research question, why use a new tool at all? Domain experts can only answer these questions for every case individually. Digital methods might solve a given problem quicker. They might reduce the input needed. They could even generate new data for further research – and their evaluation and critical reflection should be part of the implementation process.

3 Knowledge transfer

Besides the decision of the "right" research approach and the assumed problematic issues related to software already provided by other research approaches – as described above –, implementing technology into your own everyday-life research always requires time for evaluation and testing. Such an adjustment of working methods also affects the research process itself if we look at the range of new and technical different research methods, e.g. in Ancient textual studies with databases and automated statistical analysis of text register distribution (Gohy et al., 2013). The development of these kinds of new tools, such as diachronic online thesauri, accelerates philological research (Hafemann and Dils, 2013; Polis et al., 2013). The experience of some parts of the research community with this kind of acceleration of new tools to solve "old problems" is diverse, but in some way not transferable for their community peers in the humanities, e.g. Egyptology, as well as for possible cooperation partners in computer sciences.

Transferring research perspectives from humanities into computer science contexts

From the perspective of Ancient studies, there is a lot of technical integration from other disciplines, as we could see in the example of automated text categorization above (Gohy et al., 2013). From a more methodological perspective, if we stay with the field of textual studies in Ancient Egyptian, there is a diverse discourse about how methods from linguistics could widen the study of Egyptian word meaning (Grossman and Polis, 2012). This kind of knowledge transfer often does not occur automatically, and vice versa, so Ancient Studies could facilitate communication of their material's "technical basics" (cf. *Setting goals and overcoming inhibition thresholds?* in Sec. 1). Identifying the statistical modelling based on this material is a crucial step in the research process, too, as discussed above. Hence, the development of some guidelines derived from successful experiences in this field is necessary. If we stay with the example from Ancient textual studies, we probably could identify steps to communicate with computer science and vice versa:

- The composition of the Egyptian text corpora differs from the composition of corpora of more recent languages such as Arabic.¹² In cooperation with scientists from the Digital Humanities (DH) textual research field, it would be helpful to make this composition transparent.

¹¹Some companies specializing in 3D tours like Matterport already adapted and developed therefore special applications for smartphones: <https://matterport.com/de/blog/offizielle-einfuehrung-der-matterport-capture-app-fuer-android>. Similarly, DStretch has also become available as an app: <https://dstretch.com/Apps/index.html>.

¹²Cf. the paragraph about data scarcity in Egyptology in Sec. 2. Current corpora of Arabic contain between 18 and 140 million words (from newspapers) (Mansour, 2013).

- This step will help the collaboration partners identify suitable quantitative methods from the Digital Humanities perspective to process the Egyptian textual data and handle possible statistical issues.
- This "bottom-up" identified quantitative method helps transfer the study's results into informational, technological contexts. If the qualitative reading of the results from an Ancient study point of view builds on these findings, these qualitative results could also be better transferred into the discourses of other disciplines (cf. Sec. 1).

Even if the benefits seem to suit the perspective of Ancient studies as well as information technology, the challenge of defining how the experiences with new research methods and best practices of cooperation between cultural and information sciences could be made more transparent within interested research communities remains.

Knowledge transfer of interdisciplinary research outcomes within other disciplines and in communication with the public A possible answer could be using new technical possibilities to communicate project outcomes interactively and without the limits of place and time if we think, for example, of Screencast formats. A focus on digital formats like podcasts to communicate with the public could also work as a kind of collaborative accelerator to transfer outcomes of an Ancient study project into other research communities (Bartle et al., 2011). If we look at these potential target audiences, we probably need to define them more precisely (de Bruin and Bostrom, 2013):

- If we talk about the transfer of knowledge within and between research communities, we suggest a focus on sharing best practices from researchers who successfully used quantitative and qualitative methods in interdisciplinary research teams at best (cf. Sec. 1 and *Transferring research perspectives from humanities into computer science contexts* in this Section.) In this context, not only sharing the results but also including the methods as well as statistical models used to obtain the data is crucial to support researchers in identifying possible ways to evaluate and integrate new tools into their own research process.
- If we talk about communicating scientific knowledge to the public, we need to consider the importance of narratives and storytelling to connect the facts (or research outcomes) with a broader (cultural) context. This context should be relevant to the public (Dahlstrom, 2014). As stated above, these connecting factors could also help to link researchers with institutions such as museums or even stakeholders from the industry (cf. *The impact of funding and industrial cooperations* in Sec. 1).

With the issue of digital formats chosen for communication with researchers and the public, it is necessary to accommodate the needs of the target groups. To share and discuss the decision of a statistical model in a success story of interdisciplinary research, interested members of the research community would need a kind of "standardised" input of research question, material, the composition of the corpus etc. Workshops, joint conferences, bar camps, or so-called lightning talks as a short input to the discussion could help to initiate the exchange of best practices and discuss them (cf. in Sec. 1 and in Sec. 4).

The public as a target group needs concrete addressing of their needs, interests or an emotional link to topics that are relevant to them (cf. *The impact of funding and industrial cooperations* in Sec. 1). Besides podcasts, animation, interviews or a report as storytelling, the life of a prominent historical person could attract their attention, even if the topic has no direct emotional link to them. We could think here of the different portrayals of queen Nefertiti and their connection to the developments of the arts of the Amarna period. However, to strengthen this kind

of communication, Ancient studies and other disciplines should develop strategies and aims to transfer their contents and translate them for non-academics. This also requires methodological steps and the creation of concepts. Here the experiences of fields such as public history could help researchers develop sustainable communication with the public and probably also integrate the strategies and methods of communication into their research process and teaching (Fisanick and Stakeley, 2020).

4 Conclusion

We have shown throughout the paper that interdisciplinary cooperation can be extremely fruitful. Any preconceived barriers seem to be due to limitations stemming from different historical developments in the different disciplines rather than inherent barriers. Our examples indicate that the parties involved achieve mutual benefits.

The need to work together is also a result of the increasing trend towards specialisation within disciplines. Complex projects often require various domain experts who can work together closely.

In a best-case scenario, these teams can formulate new theories. The exchange of knowledge is an essential step towards reaching a big-picture goal, and integrating complementary results can further strengthen the validity and informative value of the research.

Thus, we urge researchers within and beyond Egyptology to consider interdisciplinary cooperation for their projects.

Acknowledgements

We want to express our sincere gratitude to the Federal Ministry for Education and Research Germany (BMBF) and the Hochschulrektorenkonferenz (HRK), who were third party sponsors of the KoiNet project. The workshop "New Tools for Old Problems" was made possible by Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, who provided the technical support and framework.

References

- Ernest W Adams and Nigel Strudwick. 2009. Relational database design: A tutorial and case study for egyptologists. *Information Technology and Egyptology in 2008*, pages 183–208.
- Sami Almalki. 2016. Integrating quantitative and qualitative data in mixed methods research—challenges and benefits. *Journal of education and learning*, 5(3):288–296.
- Anonymous. 2006. Iso/iec/ieee international standard for software engineering - software life cycle processes - maintenance. *ISO/IEC 14764:2006 (E) IEEE Std 14764-2006 Revision of IEEE Std 1219-1998*, pages 1–58.
- Anonymous. 2022. Iso/iec/ieee international standard - systems and software engineering – design and development of information for users. *ISO/IEC/IEEE 26514:2022(E)*, pages 1–76.
- Badisches Landesmuseum Karlsruhe, Roemer-Pelizaeus Museum Hildesheim, Qantir Excavation Project. 2019. The reconstruction of pi-ramesse. <http://www.artefacts-berlin.de/portfolio-item/the-reconstruction-of-pi-ramesse/>. Accessed: 2021-04-30.
- Emma K Bartle, Nancy Longnecker, and Mark Pegrum. 2011. Collaboration, contextualisation and communication using new media: Introducing podcasting into an undergraduate chemistry class. *International Journal of Innovation in Science and Mathematics Education*, 19(1).
- Nina Baur, Linda Hering, Anna Laura Raschke, and Cornelia Thierbach. 2014. Theory and methods in spatial analysis. towards integrating qualitative, quantitative and cartographic approaches in the social sciences and humanities. *Historical Social Research/Historische Sozialforschung*, pages 7–50.
- Berliner Antike Kolleg. 2013. Topoi editionen. https://edition-topoi.org/publishing_with_us/. Accessed: 2021-04-23.
- H Russell Bernard. 2017. *Research methods in anthropology: Qualitative and quantitative approaches*. Rowman & Littlefield.
- Amy Blackstone et al. 2018. Principles of sociological inquiry: Qualitative and quantitative methods.
- Tom B Brown, Benjamin Mann, Nick Ryder, Melanie Subbiah, Jared Kaplan, Prafulla Dhariwal, Arvind Neelakantan, Pranav Shyam, Girish Sastry, Amanda Askell, et al. 2020. Language models are few-shot learners. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2005.14165*.
- Julia Budka, Francois Bry, Christian Riepl, Sebastian Mader, and Alexander Schütze. 2016. Thot 2.0 - 5000 jahre Ägypten lernen. <https://cms-cdn.lmu.de/media/lmu/downloads/die-lmu/auszeichnungen/elearning-thot.pdf>. Accessed: 2021-04-26.
- Christian Casey. 2021. Assassin’s creed origins: Video games as time machines. *Near Eastern Archaeology*, 84(1):71–78.
- Edgar Frank Codd. 1983. A relational model of data for large shared data banks. *Communications of the ACM*, 26(1):64–69.
- Maria-Francesca Costabile, Daniela Fogli, Catherine Letondal, Piero Mussio, and Antonio Piccinno. 2003. Domain-expert users and their needs of software development. In *HCI 2003 End User Development Session*.
- John W Creswell and J David Creswell. 2017. *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*. Sage publications.
- Michael F Dahlstrom. 2014. Using narratives and storytelling to communicate science with nonexpert audiences. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 111(Supplement 4):13614–13620.
- Wändi Bruine de Bruin and Ann Bostrom. 2013. Assessing what to address in science communication. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 110(Supplement 3):14062–14068.
- Jeff Dean. 2022. Google research: Themes from 2021 and beyond. <https://ai.googleblog.com/2022/01/google-research-themes-from-2021-and.html>. Accessed: 2022-06-20.
- Jacob Devlin, Ming-Wei Chang, Kenton Lee, and Kristina Toutanova. 2019. BERT: Pre-training of deep bidirectional transformers for language understanding. In *Proceedings of the 2019 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies, Volume 1 (Long and Short Papers)*, pages 4171–4186, Minneapolis, Minnesota, June. Association for Computational Linguistics.

- Wilhelm Dilthey. 1959. *Gesammelte Schriften / 1 : Einleitung in die Geisteswissenschaften ; 1. Versuch einer Grundlegung für das Studium der Gesellschaft und der Geschichte*. Teubner, Leipzig [u.a.], 4. edition.
- Christina Fisanick and Robert O Stakeley. 2020. *Digital Storytelling as Public History: A Guidebook for Educators*. Routledge.
- Stéphanie Gohy, Benjamin Martin Leon, and Stéphane Polis. 2013. Automated text categorization in a dead language. the detection of genres in late egyptian. In *Texts, Languages & Information Technology in Egyptology. Selected papers from the meeting of the Computer Working Group of the International Association of Egyptologists (Informatique & Égyptologie)*, Liège, 6-8 July 2010, pages 61–74. Presses Universitaires de Liège.
- Olga Gonchar. 2020. Educational aspect of non-educational games: on a case study of 'assassin's creed 2' and 'assassin's creed: Origins'. *South Eastern Finland University of Applied Sciences*, page Bachelor's thesis.
- Eitan Grossman and Stéphane Polis. 2012. Lexical semantics in ancient egyptian. an introduction. *Lexical Semantics in Ancient Egyptian*, pages 1–15.
- Odd E. Gundersen. 2020. The reproducibility crisis is real. *AI Magazine*, 41(3):103–106, Fall. Accessed: 2022-06-20.
- Ingelore Hafemann and Peter Dils. 2013. Der Thesaurus Linguae Aegyptiae–Konzepte und Perspektiven. *Berlin-Brandenburgische Akademie der Wissenschaften*.
- Bashshar Haydar. 2021. The humanities' constant need for self-justification. <https://trafo.hypotheses.org/27457>. Accessed: 2022-06-20.
- Anne Herzberg. 2019. Prosopographia memphitica. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2547538>.
- Kiran Jagadeesh, Runchao Jiang, Da Li, Robert Pyke, and Lauren Wagner. 2022. Introducing the researcher platform: Empowering independent research analyzing large-scale data from meta. <https://research.facebook.com/blog/2022/1/introducing-the-researcher-platform-empowering-independent-research-analyzing-large-scale-data-from-meta/>. Accessed: 2022-06-20.
- Youssef Maguid. 2021. Why three egyptologists are teaching history through assassin's creed origins. <https://news.ubisoft.com/en-us/article/7Lp5YHoYI1N7k54Jf0JkpA/why-three-egyptologists-are-teaching-history-through-assassins-creed-origins>. Accessed: 2022-06-20.
- Mohamed Abdelmageed Mansour. 2013. The absence of arabic corpus linguistics: a call for creating an arabic national corpus. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 3(12):81–90.
- Massachusetts Institute of Technology. 1988. The MIT License (MIT). <https://mit-license.org/>. Accessed: 2022-06-20.
- Lindsay McKenzie. 2017. Swipe right for science: Papr app is 'tinder for preprints'. *Nature News*.
- Tomas Mikolov, Ilya Sutskever, Kai Chen, Greg Corrado, and Jeffrey Dean. 2013. Distributed representations of words and phrases and their compositionality. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1310.4546*.
- Gordon E Moore et al. 1965. Cramming more components onto integrated circuits.
- Heike Neuroth, Achim Oßwald, and Uwe Schwiegelshohn, 2012. *Erkenntnisse und Thesen zur Langzeitarchivierung von Forschungsdaten*, pages 311–320.
- Time Machine Organisation. 2022. Time machine. <https://www.timemachine.eu/>. Accessed: 2022-06-20.
- Perrine Poiron. 2021. Assassin's creed origins discovery tour: A behind the scenes experience. *Near Eastern Archaeology*, 84(1):79–85.
- Stéphane Polis, Anne-Claude Honnay, and Jean Winand. 2013. Building an annotated corpus of late egyptian. the ramses project: review and perspectives. In *Texts, Languages & Information Technology in Egyptology. Selected papers from the meeting of the Computer Working Group of the International Association of Egyptologists (Informatique & Égyptologie)*, Liège, 6-8 July 2010, pages 25–44. Presses Universitaires de Liège.

- Patrick Sahle. 2015. Digital humanities? gibt's doch gar nicht. *Zeitschrift für digitale Geisteswissenschaften*, 1.
- Simon Schweitzer. 2018. Corpus of Egyptian Texts for the AED - Ancient Egyptian Dictionary. <https://github.com/simondschweitzer/aed-tei>. Accessed: 2022-06-20.
- Stephan Seidlmayer. 2021. Der thesaurus linguae aegyptiae im internet. <https://aaew.bbaw.de/tla/servlet/S05?d=d001&h=h001>. Accessed: 2022-01-25.
- Shane McComas. 2018. Battlezone demo. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Ctr54kopo8I>. Accessed: 2021-04-13.
- Brett Smith. 2007. A quick guide to gplv3. *Free Software Foundation, Inc. Online: http://www.gnu.org/licenses/quick-guide-gplv3.html. Referred*, 4:2008.
- Patrik Svensson. 2012. Beyond the big tent. <https://dhdebates.gc.cuny.edu/read/untitled-88c11800-9446-469b-a3be-3fdb36bfbdl1e/section/38531431-5bd6-4eb1-95f5-fa49c025322d>. Accessed: 2022-06-20.
- Jiadai Wang, Jiajia Liu, and Nei Kato. 2019. Networking and communications in autonomous driving: A survey. *IEEE Communications Surveys Tutorials*, 21(2):1243–1274.
- Christian Wolff. 2015. The case for teaching “tool science” taking software engineering and software engineering education beyond the confinements of traditional software development contexts. In *2015 IEEE Global Engineering Education Conference (EDUCON)*, pages 932–938.